

Developmental Changes in Category-Based Inductions: The Effects of Labels and Statistical Evidence on Children's Inferences About Novel Social Categories.

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Authors Note

The work presented in this article was presented at the 2022 Society for Personality and Social Psychology Annual Convention and at the 2022 Budapest CEU Conference on Cognitive Development.

The study design, sampling plan and analysis plan were pre-registered before collecting data and can be found at <https://osf.io/gnbyp>

The data and materials have been made publicly available and can be accessed at <https://osf.io/567rw/>

Funding

This research was funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation, under the grant number P1NEP1_191722 to Magali A. Mari.

Conflict of Interests

None

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Abstract

The psychological mechanisms that subserve inductions about novel social categories in childhood are hotly debated. While research demonstrated that language, and in particular generic statements, plays a major role in how children learn to attribute properties to social categories, developmental theories propose other mechanisms. One theoretical account holds that the mere act of labeling social categories is sufficient for children to generalize properties to category members, because labels are considered as referring to significant, homogeneous kinds of people. A second theoretical account proposes that children generalize properties to category members from statistical evidence, i.e., by directly observing regularities in their environment. The present study assessed those two hypotheses, by testing (via an online experiment) the effects of simple category labels and observation of statistical evidence on European 4- to 6-year-olds ($N = 88$) and 7- to 9-year-olds' ($N = 92$) predictions about novel social categories. From around 7-9 years, children generalized properties to category members based on simple category labels or on their observation of a majority of unlabeled category members having the same property. Four- to 6-year-old children, however, made similarity inferences only when both labels and statistical evidence were combined. Overall, the present study highlights a developmental shift from an early limited tendency to make similarity inferences to a later propensity to infer similarity from small evidence. These findings deepen our understanding of the conditions under which children start to make similarity inferences. Implications for the acquisition of stereotypes are also discussed.

Keywords: social categories; category-based induction; similarity inference; statistical learning; labels

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Public Significance Statement

This study assessed two conditions under which children infer that social category members share the same properties. It highlights important developmental changes: From preschool years, language plays a crucial role in how children learn about social categories, and from early school years, children also predict that category members will be similar from their observation of regular behaviors.

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Categories are extremely useful cognitive tools for making inferences about the world, notably the social environment. Based on social category membership, children, like adults, can predict and explain new individuals' actions by drawing on past experiences (Baron, 2009; Rhodes, 2013; Rhodes & Baron, 2019). For example, if playing the piano is a known feature of social category A, then x , as a member of category A, is likely to also play the piano. Traditionally, two processes are involved in social categorization: First, children seek culturally relevant properties on which they can categorize individuals, i.e., they learn to form social categories (Baron et al., 2014; Mari, 2022; Over & McCall, 2018; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). For example, in some cultural contexts, religion may be more salient to categorize people, whereas in other contexts, categorization may be based on race or social class (Segall et al., 2015). Second, children may learn to associate certain properties (e.g., traits, roles, activities, behaviors, physical attributes, or preferences) with specific social categories (Devine, 1989; Liberman et al., 2017; Over & McCall, 2018; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). Children then make similarity inferences, expecting that members of the same social category share similar properties (Heyman & Gelman, 2000a, 2000b; Rhodes & Baron, 2019; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). Referring to the above example, children may expect that a person is good at playing the piano because they have learned that this property is characteristic of the person's social category. In the current paper, we focused on how children learn to *associate* properties with social categories, rather than on how they learn to *form* social categories.

Importantly, attributing properties to social category members is a key process in the formation of stereotypes. Stereotypes correspond to sets of expectancies about the properties of social categories, and are shared to a greater or lesser extent among people from the same

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community¹ (Klein & Bernard, 2015). On this account, social categorization and stereotyping are closely related: As one learns to associate some properties with a social category (e.g., women are caring, men are good at math), one constructs a set of stereotypical expectancies about the members of this social category (Dovidio, 1999). Therefore, a better understanding of how children generalize properties to social categories can provide key insights on the origin of stereotypes. In the following, we present two theoretical perspectives of how children learn to attribute properties to novel social categories, namely from minimal linguistic markers and from observation of statistical evidence.

A highly efficient way by which children can acquire knowledge about the social environment is through language (Gelman & Roberts, 2017; Harris, 2012). Theories of stereotyping argue that stereotype acquisition might rely on how cultural environments structure the social world by means of language, especially by labeling certain social groups (Bigler & Liben, 2006, 2007; Hirschfeld, 1996; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). Noun labels referring to categories (e.g., “she is a *carrot-eater*”, “John is an *intellectual*”) have been shown to be particularly important in shaping children’s inferences about the stability of a person’s characteristics in comparison to verbal predicates (e.g., “she eats carrots whenever she can”) or adjectives (e.g., “John is intellectual”) (Gelman & Heyman, 1999; Markman & Smith, described in Markman, 1989; Walton & Banaji, 2004). Furthermore, category labels are interpreted by children as marking social divisions (Over & McCall, 2018) and as referring to significant kinds, about which there is likely more to learn (Shutts & Kalish, 2021; Waxman & Markow, 1995). For instance, upon hearing sentences such as “Girls go to the right, boys to the left” or “The Zarpies go first, then the Gorps,” children might understand that there is something generally important about this social division and use it to make category-based

¹ Please note that stereotypes, unlike attitudes and prejudices, do not necessarily involve a positive or negative evaluation of a social category (e.g., one can hold a stereotype that homosexual couples have aesthetic flair vs. believing that homosexual couples are deviant) (Fiske & Taylor, 2013; Kurdi et al., 2019).

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inferences (Bigler & Liben, 2007; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). Category labels are thus powerful markers of social categories (Rhodes & Baron, 2019), and might have a privileged effect on how children learn about the properties of social categories and develop stereotypical expectancies.

A broad area of research has shown that category labels may license strong inferences and essentialist beliefs about social categories when combined with generic statements (e.g., “Zarpies eat flowers”, see for e.g., Baron et al., 2014; Diesendruck & Deblinger-Tangi, 2014; Foster-Hanson et al., 2019; Gelman & Markman, 1986; Jordan & Dunham, 2021; Leshin et al., 2021; Rhodes et al., 2012, 2018; Waxman & Markow, 1995). Generic language constitutes a particular form of language, conveying information about the category *as a whole* (Foster-Hanson et al., 2019; Riggs et al., 2014b) and implying that the information is essential to the identity of its referents (Bloom, 2004; Cimpian & Markman, 2011; Gelman, 2003). As such, when children are provided with information about a labeled category in the form of generic statements (e.g., “Boys are good at math,” “Zarpies play the piano”), they are prone to infer that the speaker intended to provide meaningful and relevant information that applies to *all members* of a specific *kind* of people (Foster-Hanson et al., 2019; Mari, 2022).

But is it necessary for children to hear generic statements about social categories to make similarity inferences? A few previous studies showed that children generalize properties to people that are referred to by the same label only (without generic statement), e.g., “This boy is *Jewish*,” “This one is a *Wayshan*” (Diesendruck & haLevi, 2006; Diesendruck & Weiss, 2015; Kalish, 2012; Waxman, 2010). For example, Diesendruck and haLevi (2006) provided evidence that category labels are a powerful source of information for similarity inferences. Across a series of experiments, 4- to 6-years old children were asked to predict the properties of a target character, after being introduced to two other characters that shared personality traits (e.g., “being shy”) or category membership (e.g., “being Jewish”) with the

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target. When pitted against personality traits, children were more likely to use category labels to predict the behavior of the target character (e.g., they were more likely to predict that Jewish characters, but not shy characters, will play “zaber”). In other words, children of 4-6 years old predicted that characters from the same social category (e.g., Jewish), but not with the same personality trait (e.g., shy), would share the same properties (see also Diesendruck & Weiss, 2015). Waxman (2010) further assessed the role of labels on category-based inferences. Across two experiments, children of 4 years old were introduced to individuals (e.g., a Black woman, a White woman) and their associated properties (e.g., “is good at a new game called zaggit”). In one condition, the individual was introduced with a label (e.g., “This one is a *Wayshan*”); whereas in the other condition, no label was used (e.g., “This one *eats big lunches*”). In the no-label condition, children projected the property across people in general, without taking into account race or gender. However, when individuals received arbitrary category labels, children predicted that only members of the same race (Experiment 2) or same gender (Experiment 3) would share the property. These findings provide evidence that children are sensitive to category labels and can use them to generalize properties to social category members.

However, those past studies used existing social categories, with which children were familiar and for which they might have stereotypical expectations (e.g., race, gender, or ethnicity, as in Diesendruck & haLevi, 2006; Diesendruck & Weiss, 2015; Waxman, 2010). It is possible that children readily made similarity inferences about these existing social categories because they had learned that these categories are particularly important in their cultural environment (Baron et al., 2014). It is thus not clear whether children would make similarity inferences about novel social categories – for which they have no prior knowledge – when provided with labels only. Addressing this question is particularly important regarding

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the acquisition of stereotypes, as the mere act of labeling social groups might be sufficient for children to generalize properties to group members.

Another way children might learn to associate properties with social categories is through direct observations (Chambers et al., 2008; Gelman & Roberts, 2017; Holland et al., 1986). This theoretical perspective proposes that children generalize properties to category members from statistical evidence, i.e., by observing correlations between category members and certain properties (Bigler & Liben, 2006; Gonzalez et al., 2017; Riggs, 2019). Similarly, theories of stereotyping suggest that stereotypes are acquired slowly, with accumulated experience over the lifespan (Bigler & Liben, 2006; Devine, 1989; Gonzalez et al., 2017; Greenwald & Banaji, 1995). Both perspectives draw on models of learning, proposing that children are “sophisticated pattern-detectors” (Gopnik, 2012; Riggs, 2019, p. 67), who first detect regularities in their environment, and subsequently use those regularities to make inferences (Bigler & Liben, 2006; Oakes et al., 2009; Park & Hastie, 1987; Paulus et al., 2011; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). In fact, very early on, infants are sensitive to the statistical relationships they observe in their environment. For instance, an important line of research showed that, from a very young age, children are sensitive to observed frequency when predicting an agent’s future behavior (e.g., Aloise, 1993; Boseovski & Lee, 2006; Jacobs & Narloch, 2001) and preferences (e.g., Diesendruck et al., 2015; Kushnir et al., 2010; Ma & Xu, 2011; Wellman et al., 2016). In addition, Powell and Spelke (2013) showed that from 7 months, infants expected that group members would behave similarly after observing their common behaviors. Therefore, children’s attention to correlations and regularities in their environment (e.g., seeing men working as physicists) might play a crucial role in shaping the content of stereotypes (Bigler & Liben, 2006, 2007; see also Bigler et al., 2001; Brown & Bigler, 2002; Over & McCall, 2018).

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Previous research provides evidence that children generalize properties to category members from statistical evidence. For instance, Diesendruck et al. (2015) showed that children are not only able to predict preferences of an individual based on his or her action, but also to generalize a preference to similar others. In their study, 3-4-year-olds were presented with one or two agents who selected five times the same objects from a larger set of objects. The proportion of selected objects relative to the objects available varied across conditions (namely, 18%, 50%, or 100%). Diesendruck et al. (2015) found that children inferred an agent's preference for a kind of objects when he or she selected objects in the nonrandom sampling condition, i.e., the 18% condition (see also Kushnir et al., 2010). Interestingly, when children saw two similar agents (e.g., two frogs) choosing the same type of objects, children were as likely to generalize the preference to the same agent as they were to generalize to a similar agent (i.e., to another frog) in all three conditions. These findings revealed that observing two similar agents selecting the same five objects led children to generalize the preference to a novel similar agent. In the same line, Riggs (2019) investigated whether children make similarity inferences about social category members based on statistical evidence. In this study, 4- to 8-years-old children were introduced to four members of a novel social category (e.g., a made-up country of origin) and one member from another social category (e.g., another country of origin). Children then observed four people from the same country displaying the same behavior, whereas the fifth individual, coming from another country, engaged in a different behavior. From 4 years of age, children expected that new individuals from the same country would engage in the same behaviors as their fellow category members (see also Riggs & Long, 2020; Roberts, Gelman, et al., 2017). Together, these past studies revealed that, from preschool years, children can rely on their observation of regularities to predict the behaviors and preferences of new category members.

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However, these past studies always made verbal reference to the social categories when presenting their regular actions. For example, Diesendruck et al. (2015) emphasized the identity of the new individual, by stating “Look there is another *frog* here!” (p. 374). Similarly, in Riggs’ (2019) study, for each category member presented, the country from which the member came was uttered (see also Hoicka et al., 2021; Riggs & Long, 2020; Roberts et al., 2017). This is problematic because verbally marking categories with labels has a privileged effect on how children learn about social categories, implying that similarly labeled individuals are homogeneous (Diesendruck, 2020; Over & McCall, 2018; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). It is thus not clear from past research whether children would learn to associate properties with social categories without verbal reference to the social category. This is a crucial question because it directly addresses the possibility that children might associate properties with social categories by simply observing regularities in their environment (e.g., would children associate girls with childcare after watching TV adverts of girls playing with dolls?)

The above-mentioned theories are also conditioned by some important developmental factors. Prior research showed that from preschool years, children expect that people identified by the same label would share the same properties (Diesendruck & haLevi, 2006; Diesendruck & Weiss, 2015; Waxman, 2010). These previous studies, however, used existing social categories, with which children were familiar. Therefore, it is not clear whether preschool- and school-aged children would make similarity inferences based on mere linguistic markers about *novel* social categories, for which they have no prior knowledge. One developmental perspective proposes that, with increasing linguistic competence, children become more sensitive to subtle verbal cues used to refer to social categories, such as category labels (Over & McCall, 2018). Consequently, school-aged children, but not preschoolers, may expect that members of a novel social category share the same properties

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on the basis of labels only. Moreover, previous research showed that preschoolers are more likely to generalize properties to category members than school-aged children (Kalish, 2012; Lawson & Kalish, 2006; Riggs et al., 2014b; Sherman et al., 2013). For instance, around 4-6 years, children tend to generalize properties that are presented as regularities (Riggs & Long, 2020) and to infer norms from observing regular behaviors (Roberts, Gelman, et al., 2017; Roberts, Ho, et al., 2017). As such, when observing multiple category members doing the same activity, preschoolers may be most inclined to generalize from one category member to another.

The overarching goal of the present study is to deepen our understanding of the conditions under which children start generalizing properties across members of novel social categories. One theoretical perspective holds that noun labels referring to categories signal important and meaningful social divisions, about which there is likely more to learn (Bigler & Liben, 2007; Over & McCall, 2018; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). If minimal linguistic markers are sufficient for children to generalize properties across members of novel social categories, then the way we identify social groups by means of labels might be critical for the acquisition of stereotypes. Other theoretical perspectives also propose that children might attribute properties to categories through direct observations, by detecting regularities in their environment (Bigler & Liben, 2006; Devine, 1989; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). Previous research showed that children rely on statistical evidence to make category-based inferences about verbally marked category members; but would children attribute properties to social categories from mere observation of regularities, without labeling? If they do so, then children's environment, and the images they are exposed to, might play a crucial role in the formation of stereotypes. The present study thus assessed these two theoretical perspectives by testing the effects of simple category labels and observation of

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regular actions on preschool- and school-aged children's predictions about novel social categories.

The Present Study

To understand the developmental course of similarity inferences in childhood, the present study tested two theoretical perspectives. The first perspective holds that the mere act of labeling social categories is sufficient for school-aged children, but not younger children, to generalize properties to category members (Bigler & Liben, 2007; Over & McCall, 2018; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). The second account proposes that from preschool years children can generalize properties to social category members from their observation of regularities (Bigler & Liben, 2006; Devine, 1989; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). We thus assessed whether preschoolers² (4-6 years old) and school-aged children (7-9 years old) would make similarity inferences, i.e., infer that category members share the same properties, based on category labels, observed regularities, or a combination of both. The tasks employed in the present study were inspired by typical category-based induction tasks (Diesendruck & Weiss, 2015; Gelman & Markman, 1986). Children first learned about novel social categories and their properties, and then predicted which of the properties the test exemplars would display. Children also predicted the properties of members from another social category to test whether they generalized properties consistently to only members of the same social category, and not to anyone, regardless of category membership. Novel social categories were used because they enable us to assess processes that are not tied to a specific cultural background or affected by previous experience with the social category.

² In Germany, preschool years include children between 3 and 6 years old. In the current study, all children of 6 years old had not yet entered elementary school at the time of data collection.

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In order to assess the first theoretical perspective, i.e., that simple category labels are sufficient for school-aged children to make similarity inferences, we used noun labels (e.g., “a Krollen,” “a Trielen”) to refer to social category members (see for e.g., Waxman, 2010). Whereas past studies relied on existing social categories, here, we used categories that are not deemed as meaningful and for which children had no prior knowledge to determine whether the mere act of labeling social groups prompts children to make similarity inferences. To investigate the second theoretical perspective, i.e., that observing regularities leads children to make similarity inferences, we presented a majority of unlabeled category members (6 out of 8) sharing the same property. The use of majority (6:8 ratio) rather than totality (8:8 ratio) not only ensured that we were not testing a simple case of associative learning (whereby children would learn to associate properties with anyone, regardless of their category membership), but also provided greater ecological validity (as it is rare to observe absolutely all the members of a category sharing the same properties). In the present study, the way information was presented varied across four conditions that specifically manipulated the two theoretical accounts, namely the use of category labels and direct observation of regularities: (1) Category Label (a category member was introduced with a label), (2) Observed Regularities (eight category members were introduced without label, six of which sharing the same property), (3) Interaction (combination of the Category Label and Observed Regularities conditions: eight category members were introduced with a label, six of which sharing the same property), and (4) Control (one category member was introduced without label).

As specified in our pre-registration (https://osf.io/gnbyp/?view_only=3c50cb343b474bcfb1380969769ffad8), we expected that children’s prediction scores – for both age groups – would be the lowest in the Control condition, and the highest in the Interaction condition, where both category labels and regularity cues were provided. The Category Label condition tested the hypothesis that the

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mere act of labeling social category could be sufficient for school-aged children to make similarity inferences, but not for preschoolers (Bigler & Liben, 2007; Over & McCall, 2018; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). We thus expected to find an age group difference in this condition, with 7-9-year-olds having higher prediction scores than 4-6-year-olds. The Observed Regularities condition addressed the second theoretical perspective, postulating that preschoolers may be most inclined to make similarity inferences from their observation of regular actions (Bigler & Liben, 2006; Devine, 1989; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). Accordingly, we expected that prediction scores of 4-6-year-olds children would be higher than those of 7-9-year-olds in the Observed Regularities condition. In addition, we controlled whether children, depending on their age group and the experimental condition, would make similarity inferences only for members of the same social category, and not over-generalize their predictions to members of other social categories. This later analysis was exploratory.

Methods

Participants

A total of 192 German-speaking children (53.6% female), between 4 and 9 years, participated in the study (92 4-6-year-olds and 100 7-9-year-olds). Families were asked to indicate age and gender of their child. Direct question relating to race and ethnicity were not used because these types of questions are very sensitive and unusual in Germany. Due to Covid-19 restrictions, participants were tested online through videoconference and with a Qualtrics (Provo, UT) survey. To take part in the study, families needed an internet connection and a computer/tablet to run the experiments. Only children who fluently spoke German were selected to participate in the experiments. Children were recruited from the city of Munich and its surroundings, on the basis of a lab database of interested families and of a list of families' addresses provided by the city. Families were contacted by e-mail or postal

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mail. Children's parents gave written consent at the beginning of the study and children orally assented to participate in the study. The study was approved by the institutional ethics committee and complies with American Psychological Association ethical standards. Children received a certificate and a coloring book to thank them for their participation.

Sample size was calculated a priori based on an analysis of variance for a mixed within-between-subjects design (see pre-registration, https://osf.io/gnbyp/?view_only=3c50cb343b474bcfb1380969769ffad8). Effect size assumptions were based on a pilot study conducted with 19 children, as well as on other studies that employed similar experimental designs (e.g., Riggs et al., 2014a; Roberts, Ho, et al., 2017; Shilo et al., 2021). The observed standard deviation in these studies varied between .50 and 1.50. The observed standard deviation in our pilot study was similar (1.22). Sample size calculation was thus conducted by setting the standard deviation to 1.00, with an effect size difference of .80, a type I error of .05 and a power of .80. This analysis led to a sample size estimation of 192 children. No additional participant was recruited once the predetermined sample size was reached.

As specified in the pre-registration, we excluded data from participants who stopped being attentive to the task or failed to complete the study ($n = 6$), whose responses were influenced by parents or siblings ($n = 2$), or who did not provide a correct answer to the "belonging check" question ($n = 4$). The final sample size resulted in 180 children³. Children were divided into two age groups: 4- to 6-year-olds ($n = 88$, 53.4% female, age mean = 5.49, range = 4 years 0 month to 6 years 11 months) and 7- to 9-year-olds ($n = 92$, 56.5% female, age mean = 8.50, range = 7 years 0 month to 9 years 11 months). The Category Label condition included 59 children (4-6 years: $n = 29$, age mean = 5.42; 7-9 years: $n = 30$, age mean = 8.42),

³ A post hoc analysis of power with the current sample size revealed that a power of .77 was achieved with the final sample of 180 subjects.

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the Observed Regularities condition included 59 children (4-6 years: $n = 29$, age mean = 5.46; 7-9 years: $n = 30$, age mean = 8.53), and the Interaction condition included 62 children (4-6 years: $n = 30$, age mean = 5.57; 7-9 years: $n = 32$, age mean = 8.55).

Material and Procedure

Stimuli

The stimuli consisted of short cartoon movies and were created with Microsoft PowerPoint. The cartoon illustrations were modified versions of the stimuli used by Moty & Rhodes (2021). A pre-recorded narrator guided children through the different tasks. In each task, children learned about novel categories of people distinguished by the country they came from, the language they spoke, and the types of hats they wore. Characters within each category were different with respect to their gender, ethnicity, morphology, and clothing style (see Figure 1). All study materials are available online at

https://osf.io/567rw/?view_only=43065d42d2f947a79673b7ea58be3a24.

Procedure

Upon starting the experiments, families were provided with guidelines on how to set the computer/tablet and instructions regarding parents' role during the study (e.g., parents could intervene in case of technical issues or to encourage their child, but not interfere with their child's answers). An experimenter was present through videoconference during the entire duration of the study in order to control for parents/siblings' interferences, children's attention during the tasks, and to provide support when needed. Before starting the tasks, the experimenter made sure that parents and children had understood the procedure and answered any additional questions. The experiment lasted approximately 15 minutes.

Warm-up Task. Children first completed a warm-up task to familiarize themselves with the procedure. The warm-up task started with a female narrator, introducing children to a special and distant town, where different categories of people live. Children were informed

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that they would learn about the activities of the people living in this town, and were directly presented with an example (e.g., “*Diese Person pflückt diese Blume.*”; “This person picks this flower”). Then a new character from the town was displayed, and children were asked to choose which type of flower, out of three choices, this new individual would pick (e.g., “*Was denkst du, welche Blume pflückt diese neue Person?*”; “What do you think, which flower does this new person pick?”). All children passed the warm-up task.

Introduction Phase. Children learned about two categories of people that were distinct with respect to the country they came from, the language they spoke, and the types of hats they wore (see Figure 1 for a summary of the protocol). For the Category Label and Interaction conditions, a category label was uttered twice to differentiate category members (e.g., “*Die Krollen kommen aus einem Land mit vielen Wüsten. Die Krollen tragen grüne Hüte und sprechen diese Sprache. Hör zu!*”; “The Krollens come from a country with many deserts. The Krollens wear green hats and speak this language, listen!”). Children then learned about the characteristics (i.e., language, country of origin, and hat color) associated with the other social category. Hats’ colors (red, blue, green, or orange), spoken languages (speech extracts of Chinese, Russian, Corsican, or Antillean Creole from Guadeloupe), the country’s specificities (with a lot of beaches, forests, deserts, or mountains), the position on screen (left or right), and if applicable, the label (“Trielens” or “Krollens”) associated with each social category were fully counterbalanced. Hat colors, and if applicable category labels, were used during each phase of the task to mark the two social categories. Country of origin and language were used only in the “Introduction Phase” to ensure that children considered the two sets of people as distinct social categories. This decision was motivated by the fact that very early on, children can rely on language and accent to form and distinguish social categories (Kinzler et al., 2007, 2010; Liberman et al., 2017), but it is only from 5 years of age that children start to consider clothing as marking social category boundaries (Baron et

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al., 2014; Diesendruck & Weiss, 2015). The speech extract for each selected languages consisted in recordings of native speakers reading texts⁴. The languages were selected based on the low probability that children would be familiar with these languages (according to the proportion of speakers of each language in the area of the city of Munich provided by official state statistics). To further control that children correctly learned to distinguish the two social categories, children in the present study answered two “belonging check” questions. Specifically, children were asked to link two new individuals to their corresponding category (see Figure 1, vignette 3). Children providing an incorrect answer were excluded from the study ($n = 4$).

Figure 1. *Protocol for the Introduction, Learning, and Test phases.*

⁴ The speech extracts were modified (chunks of recording were cut and pasted at different places in the track). The goal of this modification was to avoid any possible risk that if some participants spoke one of the languages played during the experiment, they would immediately assume that the group presented in the experiment was the real existing linguistic category. In addition, we also asked parents to indicate with which languages their child interacted in their daily life to further ensure that the categories presented during the experiment remained novel for the child. No participant was reported to have daily interactions with any of the languages selected for the present study.

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Introduction phase

(1) The narrator introduced the people who live in the special and distant town.

(2) The narrator highlighted the distinctions between the two novel social categories (hat colors, country, language)
 - Control / Observed Regularities: no label ("these people")
 - Label / Interaction: category labels ("Krollens"; "Trielens")

(3) Belonging check question: Participants were asked to link the new individuals to their corresponding social category.

Learning phase (4 trials)

(4) The narrator drew attention to the social category about which participants would learn (here, the green hats, on the right)

(5) The narrator introduced a new category member and her activity
 - Control / Observed Regularities: no label ("there is a new person")
 - Label / Interaction: with label ("there is a new Krollen")

(6) The narrator created a memory cue to remind participants of the property of each category member.
 (a) Control and Label conditions
 (b) Observed Regularities and Interaction conditions

Test phase (4 trials)

(7a) Prediction for the *same* category: participants attributed a property to a member of the same social category as presented in the learning phase.
 - Control / Observed Regularities: no label ("there is a new person")
 - Label / Interaction: with label ("there is a new Krollen")

(7b) Prediction for the *other* category: participants attributed a property to a member of the other social category.
 - Control / Observed Regularities: no label ("there is a new person")
 - Label / Interaction: with label ("there is a new Trielen")

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Learning Phase. Children learned about the activities performed by the members of one of the two social categories (see Figure 1, vignettes 5 and 6). There were four trials, each of which presenting one activity type. The four activity types were games (puzzles, dominos, or board games), food (peas, broccolis, or green beans), transport (scooter, roller-skates, or skateboards), and manufactured objects (pots, bowls, or baskets). The selected properties were activities because they are neither considered as too subjective (such as preferences) nor as too generalizable (such as morphological properties) (Diesendruck & Eldror, 2011; Doan et al., 2021; Riggs et al., 2014b). The way information was presented during the “Learning Phase” varied across conditions (see below). All children first completed the Control Condition before being randomly assigned to one of the test conditions, i.e., Category Label, Observed Regularities, or Interaction Condition. To ensure that children’s inferences were not influenced by repetition effects, the activities and the social categories systematically differed across the Control Condition and the Test Condition. That is, children made inferences about two different social categories and never learned about the same activity between these conditions. For example, if children learned in the Control Condition that the activity of the first social category (e.g., the red hats) was making baskets, then the activity of the second social category (e.g., the green hats) in the Test Condition was necessarily either making pots or bowls, but never baskets. In this way, information was never repeated between the Control and the Test conditions.

Control Condition. At the beginning of each trial, the narrator informed children about which characters they were going to learn (e.g., “*OK, jetzt werden wir erfahren welche Beschäftigungen diese Personen haben.*”; “Okay, now we are going to learn about the activities of these people [*animation was played on the green hats group*]”). The two social categories disappeared, and a new category member, visually marked by the color of his or her hat (e.g., red hat), appeared on the screen. Children then learned about the activity of this

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new person (e.g., “*Schau mal, das ist eine neue Person. Jetzt werden wir erfahren was sie/er herstellt.*”; “Look, there is a new person [*the category member appears on screen*]. Now we’ll find out what she/he makes [*the activity’s picture, e.g., a bowl, pops up next to the category member*]”). The category member and the picture of his or her activity then moved to the top left corner of the screen to serve as a memory cue during the “Test Phase.” The narrator explicitly informed children about this memory cue (e.g., “*Ich verschiebe, das Bild nach oben um dich daran zu erinnern, was sie/er tut.*”; “I move the picture on top to remind you what she/he does”) before moving to the “Test Phase.”

Category Label Condition. This condition is the same as the Control Condition except that the categories were introduced with a label (e.g., “*Schau mal, das ist ein neuer Kroller. Jetzt werden wir erfahren was er herstellt.*”; “Look, there is a new Krollen [*the member, e.g., with a green hat, appears on screen*]. Now we’ll find out what he makes [*the activity’s picture, e.g., a basket, pops up next to the Krollen*]”). This condition assessed the theoretical perspective that the mere act of labeling social categories leads children to generalize properties to category members (Bigler & Liben, 2007; Over & McCall, 2018; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). Again, a memory cue was provided before moving to the “Test Phase.”

Observed Regularities Condition. Children learned about the activities of eight category members, one at a time (e.g., “*Schau mal, das ist eine neue Person. Jetzt werden wir erfahren was sie/er herstellt.*”; “Look, there is a new person [*the category member, e.g., with a green hat, appears on screen*]. Now we’ll find out what she/he makes [*the activity’s picture, e.g., a basket, pops up*]” repeated for the eight members). To address the research question that children can generalize properties to category members from their observation of regularities (Bigler & Liben, 2006; Devine, 1989; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021), we presented six category members with the same activity (e.g., six members made

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baskets) and two members having different activities (e.g., one person made pots, and one person made bowls). The presentation order of each activity was randomized. A memory cue was provided for each category member, resulting in 8 memory cues displayed on the top left of the screen (see Figure 1, vignette 6b).

Interaction Condition. This condition is the same as the Observed Regularities Condition except that the categories and each member were introduced with a label (e.g., “*Schau mal, das ist ein neuer Kroller. Jetzt werden wir erfahren was er herstellt.*”; “Look, there is a new Krollen [*the member appears on screen*]. Now we’ll find out what he makes [*the activity’s picture pops up*]” repeated for eight category members). In this way, we assessed whether verbal reference to the social category is necessary for children to make similarity inference.

Test Phase. Immediately after each trial of the “Learning Phase,” the narrator invited children to predict the activities of a member from the *same* social category, and the activity of a member from the *other* social category (see Figure 1, vignettes 7a and 7b). In the Category Label and Interaction Conditions, category membership was marked by hat colors and labels (e.g., “*Schau mal ein neuer Kroller/Trieler. Was denkst du, was stellt er her?*”; “Look, a new Krollen/Trielen! What do you think, what does he make?”), whereas in the Control and Observed Regularities Conditions, category membership was only visually marked by hat colors (e.g., “*Schau mal eine neue Person. Was denkst du, was stellt er her?*”; “Look, a new person! What do you think, what does he make?”). Thus, children made predictions about an individual belonging to the *same* social category as the one presented in the “Learning Phase,” as well as about an individual belonging to the *other* category (presented in the “Introduction Phase”). The order of the questions was counter-balanced. The predictions about the *same* category members enabled us to determine if children inferred that individuals would engage in the same activities based on category membership. The

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predictions about the *other* category members enabled us to assess if children over-generalize the activity to members of another category, and not consistently to only members of the same social category. Children could select only one of the 3 possible answers for each type of activity (e.g., “pots,” “bowls,” or “baskets” for the type of made objects).

Measures and Coding

Each condition consisted in four trials, corresponding to the predictions about the four activities (games, food, transport, and object making). Children were assigned to the Control Condition and then, randomly to one of the test conditions, resulting in a total of 8 trials. For each trial, children made two category-based inductions: one about a member of the *same* category, and one about a member of the *other* category.

A prediction score was computed for each participant. Predictions were scored as 1 for a consistent response, and as 0 for an inconsistent response. A consistent response consisted in predicting the same property as the one presented in the “Learning Phase.” For example, in the Interaction Condition, participants could observe six out of eight Krollens making baskets during the Learning Phase. A consistent response for the *same* category members, in this case, consisted in predicting that a new Krollen also made baskets. If participants predicted that a new Krollen made pots or bowls, they received no point. Similarly, a consistent response for the *other* category members, in the above example, was to predict that a Trielen made baskets; no point was given if participants predicted that the Trielen made pots or bowls. Overall, participants could obtain a maximum score of 4 points per condition and per prediction type (i.e., member from the *same* or the *other* category).

Transparency and Openness

The study design, sampling and analysis plans were pre-registered before data collection at https://osf.io/gnbyp/?view_only=3c50cb343b474bcfb1380969769ffad8. We report how we determined the sample size, data exclusions, all manipulations, and all

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measures in the study. The materials, data and analyses' script have been made publicly available and can be accessed at

https://osf.io/567rw/?view_only=43065d42d2f947a79673b7ea58be3a24. The data analyses and plots were performed with RStudio, version 2022.2.2.485 (RStudio Team), using the additional packages *afex* (Singmann et al., 2016) and *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016).

Results

Difference Between the Control Condition and the Test Conditions

The Control Condition represents baseline prediction scores, as children could have used only visual cues (hat colors) to predict the properties of new category members. Comparing prediction scores for the *same* category member in the Control Condition to absolute chance (1/3 selection of the consistent property across four trials, resulting in chance = 1.333) revealed that participants in the Control Condition made category-based inferences significantly less than expected by chance ($M = 1.11$, $SD = 1.15$), $t(179) = -2.66$, $p = .009$, $d = -0.20$. To analyze if there is a difference between the Control Condition and the test conditions, i.e., that the experimental manipulation (Category Label, Observed Regularities, and Interaction Conditions) had an effect on participants' similarity inferences about members of the *same* category, we conducted three dependent *t*-tests on prediction scores, applying a Holm-Bonferroni correction (see pre-registration, https://osf.io/gnbyp/?view_only=3c50cb343b474bcfb1380969769ffad8). Prediction scores were significantly higher in the test conditions compared to the Control Condition (see Table 1).

Table 1. Prediction scores for the same social category member in the control condition compared to each test condition.

Condition	$M (SD)$ control	$M (SD)$ test	df	t	p	d
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Control - Category Label	1.08 (1.29)	1.63 (1.35)	58	4.37	<.001*	.57
Control - Observed Regularities	1.14 (1.17)	1.71 (1.29)	58	3.30	.002*	.31
Control - Interaction	1.10 (1.00)	2.00 (1.37)	61	4.46	<.001*	.36

Table 1. Statistics paired *t*-tests comparing each test condition with the control condition.

* *p*-value < adjusted *p*-value with Holm-Bonferroni correction (rank 1: adjusted *p*-value = .017; rank 2: adjusted *p*-value = .025; rank 3: adjusted *p*-value = .05).

Predictions For the Same Social Category Member

We analyzed whether age groups and test conditions would impact on children's category-based inductions. That is, we assessed whether children would attribute more often the same activities to members of the same social category depending on their age group and the test condition. As planned in the pre-registration (https://osf.io/gnbyp/?view_only=3c50cb343b474bcfb1380969769ffad8), we performed a 2 (age groups: 4-6, 7-9 years old) x 3 (test conditions: category label, observed regularities, interaction) factorial ANOVA with prediction scores for the *same* category member as dependent variable. The factorial ANOVA revealed a main effect of age groups, $F(1, 174) = 6.78$, $MSE = 1.72$, $p = .010$, $\eta_p^2 = .04$, with 7-9-year-olds having higher prediction scores ($M = 2.03$, $SD = 1.43$) than 4-6-year-olds ($M = 1.52$, $SD = 1.18$). There was, however, no main effect of the test conditions (category label, observed regularities, and interaction), $F(2, 174) = 1.38$, $MSE = 1.72$, $p = .270$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.02$, or interaction effect between age group and test conditions, $F(2, 174) = 1.28$, $MSE = 1.72$, $p = .280$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.02$.

Although no interaction effect was observed between age and condition, we nonetheless checked age group differences for each test condition, separately, as predefined in our pre-registration (even if the separate analyses were not strictly justified by the ANOVA). We thus ran independent *t*-tests for each condition, comparing prediction scores of 4-6-year-

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olds with those of 7-9-year-olds (see Figure 2). Because 3 independent *t*-tests were run, we again applied a Holm-Bonferroni correction for multiple hypotheses testing (see pre-registration, https://osf.io/gnbyp/?view_only=3c50cb343b474bcfb1380969769ffad8). The resulting adjusted *p*-values are .017, .025 and .050 for each rank respectively.

For the Category Label Condition, we expected that prediction scores of 7-9-year-olds would be higher than prediction scores of 4-6-year-olds. The *t*-test confirmed this hypothesis: 7-9-year-olds achieved higher prediction scores ($M = 2.07, SD = 1.46$) than 4-6-year-olds ($M = 1.17, SD = 1.07$), $t(57) = -2.67, p = .010$ ($< \text{adjusted } p = .017$), $d = 0.70$. When comparing younger and older children's predictions against chance, we found that younger children's performance was not different from chance level ($t(28) = -0.81, p = .425, d = -0.15$), whereas older children performed significantly above chance ($t(29) = 2.75, p = .010, d = 0.50$) (see Figure 2).

For the Observed Regularities Condition, we expected that prediction scores of 4-6-year-olds would be higher than prediction scores of 7-9-year-olds. The independent *t*-test however revealed no significant difference between the prediction scores of the 4-6-year-olds ($M = 1.45, SD = 1.02$) and the 7-9-year-olds ($M = 1.97, SD = 1.47$), $t(57) = -1.57, p = .123$ ($> \text{adjusted } p = .025$), $d = 0.41$. Again younger children's predictions were not different from chance level ($t(28) = 0.61, p = .549, d = 0.11$), but prediction scores of older children were significantly above chance ($t(29) = 2.35, p = .026, d = 0.43$) (see Figure 2).

For the Interaction Condition, we expected that prediction scores would be similar between the two age groups. Prediction scores of 4-6-year-olds ($M = 1.93, SD = 1.34$) and of 7-9-year-olds ($M = 2.06, SD = 1.41$) were in fact similar to each other, yielding no significant difference, $t(60) = -0.37, p = .713$ ($> \text{adjusted } p = .05$), $d = 0.09$. Predictions scores of both age groups were significantly above chance (younger group: $t(29) = 2.46, p = .020, d = 0.45$; older group: $t(31) = 2.92, p = .006, d = 0.52$) (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Prediction scores per conditions and age groups for members of the same social category.

Figure 2. Mean prediction scores of 4-6-year-olds and 7-9-year-olds in the Control (very light gray), Category Label (yellow/light gray), Observed Regularities (green/gray), and Interaction (blue/dark gray) conditions, with datapoints displayed. Error bars represent standard errors of the mean. The red dashed line corresponds to absolute chance level (i.e., prediction scores of 1.33).

Do Children Over-Generalize their Predictions to Members of Another Social Category?

To explore whether children over-generalized their predictions to members of another category, we performed a mixed 2 (age groups: 4-6 years, 7-9 years) x 3 (test conditions: category label, observed regularities, interaction) x 2 (category: same, other) ANOVA with prediction scores as dependent variable. The ANOVA revealed a main effect of category, $F(1, 174) = 28.29$, $MSE = 1.24$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.14$, with prediction scores that were higher for the *same* ($M = 1.78$, $SD = 1.34$) than for the *other* category member ($M = 1.15$, $SD = 1.08$).

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There was an interaction effect between age group and category, $F(1, 174) = 8.54$, $MSE = 1.24$, $p = .004$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.05$, which was the only other effect to achieve significance (all other p s $> .127$).

We conducted post-hoc analyses to further explore the difference between younger and older children's predictions for the *same* and *other* category members. Because there was no effect of condition, we collapsed prediction scores across test conditions. Post-hoc analyses revealed that 7-9-year-olds predicted consistently that only members of the same social category would share the same properties. Their prediction scores for the *same* social category member were significantly higher than for the *other* social category member, $t(91) = 5.44$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.57$. Moreover, when comparing 7-9-year-olds' prediction scores against chance, we found that 7-9-year-olds made significantly less similarity inferences for the *other* category member than expected by chance ($M = 1.07$, $SD = 1.05$), $t(91) = -2.46$, $p = .016$, $d = -0.26$. For the *same* category member, however, 7-9-year-olds made category-based inferences significantly more than expected by chance ($M = 2.03$, $SD = 1.43$), $t(91) = 4.68$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.49$ (see Figure 3).

For 4-6-year-olds, no significant difference was observed between their predictions for the *same* and the *other* social category member, $t(87) = 1.91$, $p = .060$, $d = 0.20$. Their predictions for the member of the *same* ($M = 1.52$, $SD = 1.18$) and *other* ($M = 1.24$, $SD = 1.11$) social category were not significantly different from chance level (same: $t(87) = 1.50$, $p = .137$, $d = 0.16$; other: $t(87) = -0.80$, $p = .428$, $d = -0.08$) (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Prediction scores for the *same* and the *other* category members per age groups.

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Figure 3. Mean prediction scores of 4-6-year-olds and 7-9-year-olds obtained for the *same* (yellow/light gray) and the *other* (blue/dark gray) category members, with datapoints displayed. Error bars represent standard errors of the mean. The red dashed line corresponds to absolute chance level (i.e., prediction scores of 1.33).

Discussion

The current research investigated two theoretical perspectives proposing that children learn to associate properties with social categories from *simple category labels* (Bigler & Liben, 2007; Over & McCall, 2018; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021), or from their *observation of regularities* (Bigler & Liben, 2006; Devine, 1989; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). It took a developmental perspective by comparing preschool- (4-6 years) and school-aged (7-9 years) children's similarity inferences about social category members. More concretely, we assessed whether children predicted that an individual would engage in the same activity as its fellow-category members after being exposed to (a) simple linguistic markers of social category, i.e., one category member referred to by a label, (b) mere observation of regularities, i.e., observing a majority of unlabeled category members doing the same activity, (c) simple category labels and observed regularities, i.e., observing a

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majority of labeled category members doing the same activity, and (d) a control condition, i.e., a single category member introduced without label.

Overall, the present study supports and extends the theoretical perspective that children learn to associate properties with social categories from their observation of regularities (Bigler & Liben, 2006; Devine, 1989; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). Previous research revealed that from 4 years old, children can rely on statistical evidence to predict the properties of social category members (e.g., Diesendruck et al., 2015; Riggs, 2019). However, these past studies verbally marked the identity of category members upon presenting their regular actions. In the present study, two conditions were created to separately assess whether children would associate properties with social categories from their observation of regular actions, with or without category labels. On the one hand, 7-9-year-olds, but not 4-6-year-olds, made similarity inference from observing a majority of *unlabeled* category members engaging in the same activity. On the other hand, and similar to previous research (Diesendruck et al., 2015; Riggs, 2019; Roberts, Gelman, et al., 2017), from preschool age, children made similarity inferences from statistical evidence when labels were provided. These findings support the theoretical perspective that, as early as the preschool years, children generalize properties to verbally marked category members from their observation of regularities (Bigler & Liben, 2006; Devine, 1989; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). Moreover, the present study adds novel perspective to this theoretical account, showing that around 7-9 years, children start to make similarity inferences from the regularities they observe, without needing labels.

The present study also confirms the theoretical perspective that the mere act of labeling social categories is sufficient for school-aged children, but not preschoolers, to generalize properties to category members (Bigler & Liben, 2007; Over & McCall, 2018; Sherman et al., 2013; Shutts & Kalish, 2021). From 7-9 years, children could make similarity

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inferences based on simple category labels; younger children failed to generalize properties from simply learning about the property of *one* labeled individual. These results complement previous findings that showed that preschoolers are prone to generalize properties across category members (e.g., Diesendruck & haLevi, 2006; Diesendruck & Weiss, 2015; Kalish, 2012; Rhodes & Gelman, 2008; Waxman, 2010), and should be interpreted in the light of two important considerations. First, the present study differs from previous research in the degree to which the tested social categories were essentialized. Previous research revealed that from preschool years, children readily associate attributes with *existing* social categories (e.g., Diesendruck & haLevi, 2006; Gelman et al., 1986; Rhodes & Gelman, 2008; Waxman, 2010, for a review see Charlesworth & Banaji, in press). This is because existing social categories tend to be highly essentialized, leading children to assume that category members share the same properties because of an underlying essence (Diesendruck, 2020; Mari, 2022). Children, however, do not hold these kinds of essentialist beliefs about novel artificial categories (Hoicka et al., 2021; Leshin et al., 2021; Rhodes, 2013; Vasilyeva et al., 2018). Second, the present study assessed whether children could draw similarity inferences from mere labels, rather than labels in combination with generic language. As previously discussed, generic language constitutes a privileged cultural input that guides children's inferences and essentialist beliefs about social categories (Bloom, 2004; Cimpian & Markman, 2011; Gelman, 2003). And indeed, an important number of studies documented that using labels with generic statements prompted preschoolers to assume that *any* properties are generalizable to members of the same *novel* social category (e.g., Baron et al., 2014; Jordan & Dunham, 2021; Moty & Rhodes, 2021; Rhodes et al., 2012, for a review, see Mari, 2022). The present study thus specifies previous findings, showing that the mere act of labeling individuals might not be sufficient for young children to attribute properties to members of novel artificial social categories. Yet, as children develop increased linguistic competence and

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experience school settings and peer interactions, they also become more sensitive to mere verbal cues to social categories (Over & McCall, 2018). In other words, from early school years, children start to consider mere labels as meaningful markers of social divisions.

In addition, our study provides some clarifications regarding the extent to which children make similarity inferences. To our knowledge, previous studies did not assess whether children generalize properties to only members of the *same* social category or if they tend to *over-generalize* the properties to any individuals, regardless of their social category. This distinction is theoretically important in determining whether the social category *per se* had inductive force, and in ruling out the possibility that children projected properties onto people in general (Shutts et al., 2013; Waxman, 2010). An exploratory analysis was conducted to assess this question and revealed that 7-9-year-olds predicted that only members of the same social category would engage in similar activities; their predictions for the members of another social category were at chance level. Younger children, in contrast, failed to expect that only members of the same social category would engage in similar activities. Overall, these results suggest that from 7-9 years old, children start to generalize properties consistently to only members of the same novel social categories from minimal linguistic markers or mere observation of regularities.

One could argue that the seemingly low generalization rates observed among younger children might be due to the online administration of the tasks, which might have had an impact on younger children's attention. However, we doubt this was the case as several strategies have been applied to ensure that children would remain attentive during the task and to reduce the possible demands of the study. First, we provided breaks between trials, thereby offering children the possibility to make a pause if they needed to. Second, for the younger children, parents were present to help them using the computer/tablet and, if necessary, to support and encourage them during the task. Third, the experimenter verified that the children

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were attentive for the whole duration of the study. Data from children who stopped paying attention to the task were excluded (cf. Methods' section). What is more, a growing number of research in developmental psychology started to evaluate the validity of online testing, and demonstrated that online studies yielded similar results as in-person studies (for e.g., Rhodes et al., 2020; Schidelko et al., 2021; Vales et al., 2021; Yamamoto et al., 2021). In particular, Rhodes et al. (2020) conducted online several studies that were originally face-to-face, with paradigms similar to the one presented here, and with children of the same age range (between 4 and 8 years old). Their online replications yielded results similar to the in-person studies, suggesting that these kinds of paradigms (i.e., where children listen to simple stories and respond by choosing between pictured response options) are well suited for online testing with children from 4 years old (Rhodes et al., 2020, see also Schidelko et al., 2021).

In future work, it will be important to examine the interaction between different types of properties and category-based induction processes. In fact, previous research showed that certain properties are more likely generalized across category members than others. For example, children are prone to expect that members of novel social categories share morphological features and psychological properties (Diesendruck & Eldror, 2011; Riggs et al., 2014b) but not preferences or historical properties (Doan et al., 2021; Riggs et al., 2014b). In the present study, we tried to select properties that offered a trade-off between very subjective properties (e.g., preferences) and very generalizable properties (e.g., morphological features, psychological traits). It is possible that preschoolers might be more inclined to make similarity inferences when the properties are viewed as more generalizable. For example, using less common, more distinctive properties, such as unusual behaviors (e.g., "raising arms," Riggs, 2019) or novel properties (e.g., "eating a new snack called *naggle*," Waxman, 2010), might help younger children to make more similarity inferences. In fact, determining which properties are better source of inductive potential represents an interesting avenue for

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future research (cf. Diesendruck & Eldror, 2011). In the future, researchers should thus take into account the large variety of attributes that can be associated with social category members (e.g., traits, roles, skills, behaviors, beliefs, preferences, interpersonal relations, or physical features), and systematically assess how the type of attributes modulates category-based inferences.

Furthermore, one question raised by our experimental design is whether the choice to use familiar properties without additional element of contrast evidence played a role on the overall pattern of the results. Because the properties selected for the present study were familiar, children might have prior biases regarding these properties, inferring that people would display each property to similar extent. As such, receiving evidence that category members engage in one activity (e.g., “the Krollens make baskets”), without contrasting evidence (e.g., “the Krollens *do not* make pots or bowls”) might have confirmed children’s preconceptions and might have been insufficient to compete with their prior expectations, thereby leading to limited generalization rates. In fact, previous studies, that presented positive *and* negative evidence about the properties of social categories, found overall higher generalization rates among children between 4 and 6 years old (e.g., Foster-Hanson et al., 2021; Kalish, 2012; Roberts, Gelman, et al., 2017; Roberts, Ho, et al., 2017). In these studies, children simultaneously learned about the contrasting properties of two different social categories. This setup might have prompted children to perceive some degree of competition between the social categories, which would, in turn, increase their generalization of properties to social category members (Rhodes & Brickman, 2011; Riggs & Long, 2020). The current research, however, built on the theoretical perspectives that children can learn about the properties of one social category from mere labels or from their observation of regularities. The exact role of contrasting negative evidence in this learning process remains unclear. It is possible that the youngest children would make more similarity inferences based on small

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evidence, if they were provided with additional information that explicitly presents the properties as mutually exclusive (see for e.g., research on general word learning, Markman, 1987; Markman & Wachtel, 1988; Zosh et al., 2013). Future research should thus systematically consider the role of prior biases and the need of contrasting negative evidence when assessing children's inductive inferences about social categories.

Two limitations to the current research should also be mentioned. First, the present study lacks a better appreciation of the amount of statistical evidence children need to start making similarity inferences. Because the study was conducted online, we had to limit the duration of the experiment to keep children motivated. Therefore, the number of observations had to be restricted to eight category members. We have to leave it to future research to test varying frequencies, such as 60%, 70%, 80%, or 90%, and increase the number of observed instances (e.g., presenting 10, 15, 20 category members) to determine if there is a threshold from which children start to make similarity inferences based on their observation of regularities. Second, the data derived from a sample of European children, and therefore prevent us from drawing conclusions about children's similarity inferences across human populations. Future cross-cultural research, including underrepresented populations, would provide a better and more nuanced understanding of how children learn about social groups.

In sum, the capacity to make similarity inferences about social categories has cognitive advantages, reducing the complexity of the social world and allowing children to predict and explain category members' features and behaviors (Baron, 2009; Rhodes, 2013; Rhodes & Baron, 2019), but it also sets the ground for the development of stereotypes (Bigler & Liben, 2006; Rhodes & Baron, 2019; Tajfel, 1970). The present study suggests that early school years might be a critical period in which children start to easily attribute properties to social categories from minimal cues. This finding bears some important implications. First, the mere act of labeling social groups (e.g., "Girls go to the right, boys to the left," "Joe is a

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vegetarian”) might prompt school-aged children to infer that similarly labeled people will share the same properties. Second, school-aged children also seem to be prone to attribute properties to social categories by observing regularities in their environment (e.g., observing a majority of men physicists, of shy librarians, etc.). Third, young children were more conservative in their generalization, attributing properties to social category members on the basis of labels *and* regular actions. This reluctance to make similarity inferences from small evidence could in fact prevent young children from making overly broad generalizations in the process of early conceptual development (cf. Brandone et al., 2015). As such, it seems particularly important to monitor how social categories are represented and referred to during these age periods to possibly reduce some stereotyping effects.

Taken together, the present study’s results suggest that from 7-9 years, children readily pick up information about social categories, and infer that new individuals, belonging to the same category, will be similar. The present study suggests that this tendency to rapidly make similarity inferences develops during the early school years and may constitute the ground from which children acquire stereotypes.

References

- Aloise, P. A. (1993). Trait confirmation and disconfirmation: The development of attribution biases. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, *55*(2), 177–193.
<https://doi.org/10.1006/jecp.1993.1010>
- Baron, A. S. (2009). *Foundations of intergroup cognition* [Dissertation, Harvard University]. Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global database. (UMI No. 3395407)
- Baron, A. S., Dunham, Y., Banaji, M., & Carey, S. (2014). Constraints on the acquisition of social category concepts. *Journal of Cognition and Development*, *15*(2), 238–268.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15248372.2012.742902>
- Bigler, R. S., & Liben, L. S. (2006). A developmental intergroup theory of social stereotypes and prejudice. *Advances in Child Development and Behavior*, *34*, 39–89.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0065-2407\(06\)80004-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0065-2407(06)80004-2)
- Bigler, R. S., & Liben, L. S. (2007). Developmental Intergroup Theory: Explaining and reducing children’s social stereotyping and prejudice. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, *16*(3), 162–166. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8721.2007.00496.x>
- Bigler, R. S., Spears Brown, C., & Markell, M. (2001). When groups are not created equal: Effects of group status on the formation of intergroup attitudes in children. *Child Development*, *72*(4), 1151–1162. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8624.00339>
- Bloom, P. (2004). *Descartes’ baby: How the science of child development explains what makes us human*. Basic Books.
- Boseovski, J. J., & Lee, K. (2006). Children’s use of frequency information for trait categorization and behavioral prediction. *Developmental Psychology*, *42*(3), 500–513.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.42.3.500>

INFERENCE FROM LABELS AND STATISTICAL EVIDENCE

Brandone, A. C., Gelman, S. A., & Hedglen, J. (2015). Children's developing intuitions about the truth conditions and implications of novel generics versus quantified statements.

Cognitive Science, 39(4), 711–738. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.12176>

Brown, C. S., & Bigler, R. S. (2002). Effects of minority status in the classroom on children's intergroup attitudes. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 83(2), 77–110.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0965\(02\)00123-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0965(02)00123-6)

Chambers, C. G., Graham, S. A., & Turner, J. N. (2008). When hearsay trumps evidence: How generic language guides preschoolers' inferences about unfamiliar things.

Language and Cognitive Processes, 23(5), 749–766.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01690960701786111>

Charlesworth, T. E. S., & Banaji, M. R. (n.d.). The development of social group cognition:

What infants and young children can teach us. In *Oxford Handbook of Social Cognition* (2nd Edition). Retrieved May 30, 2022, from

http://www.people.fas.harvard.edu/~banaji/research/publications/articles/2021_Charlesworth_OHSC.pdf

Cimpian, A., & Markman, E. M. (2011). The generic/nongeneric distinction influences how children interpret new information about social others. *Child Development*, 82(2), 471–

492. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2010.01525.x>

Devine, P. G. (1989). Stereotypes and prejudice: Their automatic and controlled components.

Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 56(1), 5–18.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.56.1.5>

Diesendruck, G. (2020). Why do children essentialize social groups? In *Advances in Child Development and Behavior* (Vol. 59, pp. 31–64). Elsevier.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.acdb.2020.05.002>

INFERENCE FROM LABELS AND STATISTICAL EVIDENCE

- Diesendruck, G., & Deblinger-Tangi, R. (2014). The linguistic construction of social categories in toddlers. *Child Development, 85*(1), 114–123.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12130>
- Diesendruck, G., & Eldror, E. (2011). What children infer from social categories. *Cognitive Development, 26*(2), 118–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogdev.2010.11.001>
- Diesendruck, G., & haLevi, H. (2006). The role of language, appearance, and culture in children's social category-based induction. *Child Development, 77*(3), 539–553.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2006.00889.x>
- Diesendruck, G., Salzer, S., Kushnir, T., & Xu, F. (2015). When choices are not personal: The effect of statistical and social cues on children's inferences about the scope of preferences. *Journal of Cognition and Development, 16*(2), 370–380.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15248372.2013.848870>
- Diesendruck, G., & Weiss, E. (2015). Children's differential weighting of cues to social categories. *Cognitive Development, 33*, 56–72.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogdev.2014.06.001>
- Doan, T., Friedman, O., & Denison, S. (2021). Toddlers and preschoolers understand that some preferences are more subjective than others. *Child Development, 92*(3), 853–861.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13581>
- Dovidio, J. F. (1999). Stereotyping. In R. A. Wilson & F. C. Keil (Eds.), *The MIT Encyclopedia of the Cognitive Science* (pp. 804–806). MIT Press.
<https://www.proquest.com/books/mit-encyclopedia-cognitive-sciences/docview/619413801/se-2?accountid=14610>
- Fiske, S. T., & Taylor, S. E. (2013). *Social cognition: From brains to culture*. Sage.

INFERENCE FROM LABELS AND STATISTICAL EVIDENCE

- Foster-Hanson, E., Leslie, S.-J., & Rhodes, M. (2019). Speaking of kinds: How generic language shapes the development of category representations. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/28qf7>.
- Foster-Hanson, E., Roberts, S. O., Gelman, S. A., & Rhodes, M. (2021). Categories convey prescriptive information across domains and development. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 212, 105231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2021.105231>
- Gelman, S. A. (2003). *The Essential Child*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195154061.001.0001>
- Gelman, S. A., Collman, P., & Maccoby, E. E. (1986). Inferring properties from categories versus inferring categories from properties: The case of gender. *Child Development*, 57(2), 396–404. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1130595>
- Gelman, S. A., & Heyman, G. D. (1999). Carrot-eaters and creature-believers: The effects of lexicalization on children's inferences about social categories. *Psychological Science*, 10(6), 489–493. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9280.00194>
- Gelman, S. A., & Markman, E. M. (1986). Categories and induction in young children. *Cognition*, 23(3), 183–209. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0277\(86\)90034-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0277(86)90034-X)
- Gelman, S. A., & Roberts, S. O. (2017). How language shapes the cultural inheritance of categories. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(30), 7900–7907. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1621073114>
- Gonzalez, A. M., Dunlop, W. L., & Baron, A. S. (2017). Malleability of implicit associations across development. *Developmental Science*, 20(6), e12481. <https://doi.org/10.1111/desc.12481>
- Gopnik, A. (2012). Scientific thinking in young children: Theoretical advances, empirical research, and policy implications. *Science*, 337(6102), 1623–1627. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1223416>

INFERENCE FROM LABELS AND STATISTICAL EVIDENCE

- Greenwald, A. G., & Banaji, M. R. (1995). Implicit social cognition: Attitudes, self-esteem, and stereotypes. *Psychological Review*, *102*(1), 4–27. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.102.1.4>
- Harris, P. L. (2012). *Trusting what you're told: How children learn from others*. Harvard University Press.
- Heyman, G. D., & Gelman, S. A. (2000a). Preschool children's use of novel predicates to make inductive inferences about people. *Cognitive Development*, *15*(3), 263–280. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-2014\(00\)00028-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-2014(00)00028-9)
- Heyman, G. D., & Gelman, S. A. (2000b). Preschool children's use of trait labels to make inductive inferences. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, *77*(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jecp.1999.2555>
- Hirschfeld, L. A. (1996). *Race in the making: Cognition, culture, and the child's construction of human kinds*. The MIT Press.
- Hoicka, E., Saul, J., Prouten, E., Whitehead, L., & Sterken, R. (2021). Language signaling high proportions and generics lead to generalizing, but not essentializing, for novel social kinds. *Cognitive Science*, *45*(11), e13051. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.13051>
- Holland, J. H., Holyoak, K. J., Nisbett, R. E., & Thagard, P. R. (1986). *Induction: Processes of inference, learning, and discovery*. MIT Press.
- Jacobs, J. E., & Narloch, R. H. (2001). Children's use of sample size and variability to make social inferences. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, *22*(3), 311–331. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0193-3973\(01\)00086-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0193-3973(01)00086-7)
- Jordan, A., & Dunham, Y. (2021). Are category labels primary? Children use similarities to reason about social groups. *Developmental Science*, *24*(2), e13013. <https://doi.org/10.1111/desc.13013>

INFERENCE FROM LABELS AND STATISTICAL EVIDENCE

Kalish, C. W. (2012). Generalizing norms and preferences within social categories and individuals. *Developmental Psychology*, *48*(4), 1133–1143.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0026344>

Kinzler, K. D., Dupoux, E., & Spelke, E. S. (2007). The native language of social cognition. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *104*(30), 12577–12580.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0705345104>

Kinzler, K. D., Shutts, K., & Correll, J. (2010). Priorities in social categories. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, *40*(4), 581–592. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.739>

Klein, O., & Bernard, P. (2015). Stereotypes in social psychology. In J. D. Wright (Ed.), *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences* (pp. 446–452). Elsevier.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.24097-X>

Kurdi, B., Mann, T. C., Charlesworth, T. E. S., & Banaji, M. R. (2019). The relationship between implicit intergroup attitudes and beliefs. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *116*(13), 5862–5871.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1820240116>

Kushnir, T., Xu, F., & Wellman, H. M. (2010). Young children use statistical sampling to infer the preferences of other people. *Psychological Science*, *21*(8), 1134–1140.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797610376652>

Lawson, C. A., & Kalish, C. W. (2006). Inductive inferences across time and identity: Are category members more alike than single individuals? *Journal of Cognition and Development*, *7*(2), 233–252. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327647jcd0702_5

Leshin, R. A., Leslie, S., & Rhodes, M. (2021). Does it matter how we speak about social kinds? A large, preregistered, online experimental study of how language shapes the development of essentialist beliefs. *Child Development*, *92*(4), e531–e547.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13527>

INFERENCE FROM LABELS AND STATISTICAL EVIDENCE

- Lieberman, Z., Woodward, A. L., & Kinzler, K. D. (2017). The origins of social categorization. In *Trends in Cognitive Sciences* (Vol. 21, Issue 7, pp. 556–568). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2017.04.004>
- Ma, L., & Xu, F. (2011). Young children's use of statistical sampling evidence to infer the subjectivity of preferences. *Cognition*, *120*(3), 403–411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2011.02.003>
- Mari, M. A. (2022). How cues to social categorization impact children's inferences about social categories. *Acta Psychologica*, *229*(103707), 1–12. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2022.103707>
- Markman, E. M. (1987). How children constrain the possible meanings of words. In U. Neisser (Ed.), *Concepts and conceptual development: Ecological and intellectual factors in categorization* (pp. 255–287). Cambridge University Press.
- Markman, E. M. (1989). *Categorization and naming in children: Problems of induction*. MIT Press.
- Markman, E. M., & Wachtel, G. F. (1988). Children's use of mutual exclusivity to constrain the meanings of words. *Cognitive Psychology*, *20*(2), 121–157. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0285\(88\)90017-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0285(88)90017-5)
- Moty, K., & Rhodes, M. (2021). The unintended consequences of the things we say: What generic statements communicate to children about unmentioned categories. *Psychological Science*, *32*(2), 189–203. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797620953132>
- Oakes, L. M., Horst, J. S., Kovack-Lesh, K. A., & Perone, S. (2009). How infants learn categories. In A. Woodward & A. Needham (Eds.), *Learning and the Infant Mind* (pp. 144–171). Oxford University Press.

INFERENCE FROM LABELS AND STATISTICAL EVIDENCE

Over, H., & McCall, C. (2018). Becoming us and them: Social learning and intergroup bias.

Social and Personality Psychology Compass, 12(4), e12384.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/spc3.12384>

Park, B., & Hastie, R. (1987). Perception of variability in category development: Instance-

versus abstraction-based stereotypes. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*,

53(4), 621–635. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.53.4.621>

Paulus, M., Hunnius, S., van Wijngaarden, C., Vrins, S., van Rooij, I., & Bekkering, H.

(2011). The role of frequency information and teleological reasoning in infants' and adults' action prediction. *Developmental Psychology*, 47(4), 976–983.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0023785>

Powell, L. J., & Spelke, E. S. (2013). Preverbal infants expect members of social groups to act alike. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 110(41).

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1304326110>

Rhodes, M. (2013). How two intuitive theories shape the development of social categorization. *Child Development Perspectives*, 7(1), 12–16.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdep.12007>

Rhodes, M., & Baron, A. (2019). The development of social categorization. *Annual Review of Developmental Psychology*, 1, 359–386. [https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-devpsych-](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-devpsych-121318-084824)

121318-084824

Rhodes, M., & Brickman, D. (2011). The influence of competition on children's social categories. *Journal of Cognition and Development*, 12(2), 194–221.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/15248372.2010.535230>

Rhodes, M., & Gelman, S. A. (2008). Categories influence predictions about individual consistency. *Child Development*, 79(5), 1270–1287. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2008.01188.x)

8624.2008.01188.x

INFERENCE FROM LABELS AND STATISTICAL EVIDENCE

Rhodes, M., Leslie, S. J., Bianchi, L., & Chalik, L. (2018). The role of generic language in the early development of social categorization. *Child Development, 89*(1), 148–155.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12714>

Rhodes, M., Leslie, S.-J., & Tworek, C. M. (2012). Cultural transmission of social essentialism. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 109*(34), 13526–13531.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1208951109>

Rhodes, M., Rizzo, M. T., Foster-Hanson, E., Moty, K., Leshin, R. A., Wang, M., Benitez, J., & Ocampo, J. D. (2020). Advancing developmental science via unmoderated remote research with children. *Journal of Cognition and Development, 21*(4), 477–493.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/15248372.2020.1797751>

Riggs, A. E. (2019). Social statistics: Children use statistical reasoning to guide their inferences about the scope of social behavior. *Developmental Psychology, 55*(1), 66–79.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0000618>

Riggs, A. E., Kalish, C. W., & Alibali, M. W. (2014a). When you've seen one, have you seen them all? Children's memory for general and specific learning episodes. *Developmental Psychology, 50*(6), 1653–1659. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0036130>

Riggs, A. E., Kalish, C. W., & Alibali, M. W. (2014b). Property content guides children's memory for social learning episodes. *Cognition, 131*(2), 243–253.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2014.01.004>

Riggs, A. E., & Long, M. (2020). The Domain Frequency Association: A mental shortcut to guide children's generalization of norms and preferences. *Cognitive Development, 54*, 100853. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogdev.2020.100853>

Roberts, S. O., Gelman, S. A., & Ho, A. K. (2017). So it is, so it shall be: Group regularities license children's prescriptive judgments. *Cognitive Science, 41*, 576–600.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.12443>

INFERENCE FROM LABELS AND STATISTICAL EVIDENCE

- Roberts, S. O., Ho, A. K., & Gelman, S. A. (2017). Group presence, category labels, and generic statements influence children to treat descriptive group regularities as prescriptive. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology, 158*, 19–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2016.11.013>
- Schidelko, L. P., Schünemann, B., Rakoczy, H., & Proft, M. (2021). Online testing yields the same results as lab testing: A validation study with the False Belief Task. *Frontiers in Psychology, 12*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.703238>
- Segall, G., Birnbaum, D., Deeb, I., & Diesendruck, G. (2015). The intergenerational transmission of ethnic essentialism: How parents talk counts the most. *Developmental Science, 18*(4), 543–555. <https://doi.org/10.1111/desc.12235>
- Sherman, S. J., Sherman, J. W., Percy, E. J., & Soderberg, C. K. (2013). Stereotype Development and Formation. In D. Carlston (Ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Social Cognition* (pp. 548–574). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199730018.013.0027>
- Shilo, R., Weinsdörfer, A., Rakoczy, H., & Diesendruck, G. (2021). Children’s prediction of others’ behavior based on group vs. individual properties. *Cognitive Development, 57*, 100955. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogdev.2020.100955>
- Shutts, K., & Kalish, C. W. (2021). Intuitive sociology. In *Advances in Child Development and Behavior* (Vol. 61, pp. 335–374). Academic Press Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.acdb.2021.05.004>
- Shutts, K., Roben, C. K. P., & Spelke, E. S. (2013). Children’s use of social categories in thinking about people and social relationships. *Journal of Cognition and Development, 14*(1), 35–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15248372.2011.638686>
- Singmann, H., Bolker, B., Westfall, J., Aust, F., & Ben-Shachar, M. S. (2016). *afex: Analysis of Factorial Experiments*.

INFERENCE FROM LABELS AND STATISTICAL EVIDENCE

- Tajfel, H. (1970). Experiments in intergroup discrimination. *Scientific American*, 223(5), 96–102.
- Vales, C., Wu, C., Torrance, J., Shannon, H., States, S. L., & Fisher, A. v. (2021). Research at a distance: Replicating semantic differentiation effects using remote data collection with children participants. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.697550>
- Vasilyeva, N., Gopnik, A., & Lombrozo, T. (2018). The development of structural thinking about social categories. *Developmental Psychology*, 54(9), 1735–1744.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0000555>
- Walton, G. M., & Banaji, M. R. (2004). Being what you say: The effect of essentialist linguistic labels on preferences. *Social Cognition*, 22(2), 193–213.
<https://doi.org/10.1521/soco.22.2.193.35463>
- Waxman, S. R. (2010). Names will never hurt me? Naming and the development of racial and gender categories in preschool-aged children. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 40(4), 593–610. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.732>
- Waxman, S. R., & Markow, D. B. (1995). Words as invitations to form categories: Evidence from 12- to 13-month-old infants. *Cognitive Psychology*, 29(3), 257–302.
<https://doi.org/10.1006/cogp.1995.1016>
- Wellman, H. M., Kushnir, T., Xu, F., & Brink, K. A. (2016). Infants use statistical sampling to understand the psychological world. *Infancy*, 21(5), 668–676.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/infa.12131>
- Wickham, H. (2016). *ggplot2: Elegant graphics for data analysis*. Springer-Verlag.
- Yamamoto, H. W., Kawahara, M., & Tanaka, A. (2021). A web-based auditory and visual emotion perception task experiment with children and a comparison of lab data and web data. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.702106>

INFERENCE FROM LABELS AND STATISTICAL EVIDENCE

Zosh, J. M., Brinster, M., & Halberda, J. (2013). Optimal contrast: Competition between two referents improves word learning. *Applied Developmental Science, 17*(1), 20–28.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2013.748420>

Mari, M. A., Clément, F., & Paulus, M. (2022, November 22). Developmental Changes in Category-Based Inductions: The Effects of Labels and Statistical Evidence on Children's Inferences About Novel Social Categories. Retrieved from <https://osf.io/567rw/>.